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NON-NATIVE CHILD BILINGUALISM: PECULIARITIES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

In this article, we discuss advantages and disadvantages of bilingualism, compared to monolingualism; review different strategies of bilingual development and challenges families may face; focus on bilingualism in non-native families outside English-speaking context; and compare two kinds of bilingual development (Bilingual First Language Acquisition (BFLA) and Early Second Language Acquisition (ESLA)).

Keywords: bilingualism, non-native bilingualism, bilingual first language acquisition, early second language acquisition.

Introduction

Child bilingualism is a widespread global phenomenon, though precise statistics are not available. It occurs in different context and for different reasons, in the first place, under influence of objective circumstances, like need for communication and social integration in immigrant and international families, but more and more people make a deliberate choice in favor of raising their children as bilinguals, due to benefits this kind of education promises in terms of social success and cognitive development. As a consequence, there has been an increase in artificially created bilingual contexts, when for communication with their child, parents choose the language, that is neither native to them, nor spoken in the society where the family lives. According to Romanowski (1), who surveyed non-native bilingual (NNB) Polish families, reasons for bilingual upbringing often are: 1. Perceiving a foreign language as a gift enabling a child to experience the world and different cultures first-hand, using it in a free and natural manner. It is important for parents to prevent their children from learning a language in an imposed mode. 2. Foreign language skills are viewed as broadening children's horizons. 3. Intellectual profits and enhanced cognitive development. 4. Practical reasons, such as visiting relatives living abroad, or coping with the foreign language-speaking environment on family's regular business trips.

As argued by De Houwer (2), the term 'bilingual children' refers to typically developing, normally hearing children under age 12 who need to learn to communicate in more than a single language in daily life, leaving unspecified to what extent children are able to communicate in two languages. Another characteristic is that the acquisition of these languages should be untutored and naturalistic, most often occurring as a result of life circumstances that are not easy to change.

Pros and cons for bilingualism-monolingualism from the point of linguistic and cognitive development

Among advantages of bilingual development, research mentions the following:

1. Advantages in vocabulary acquisition

De Houwer (2, 3) argued that 13-month-old Bilingual First Language Acquisition (BFLA) children understand 70% more words than matched monolingual children, including potentially bilingual and Early Second Language Acquisition (ESLA) children. BFLA infants reach a certain amount of total vocabulary 4 more months earlier, than monolingual children. By 13 months, BFLA infants understand translation equivalents.

2. Higher speech processing speed

Serratrice (4) stated that vocabulary size was the feature to which efficiency with the processing of the speech signal in bilingual toddlers was linked; in a study of Spanish-English 2-year-olds' lexicons in a preferential looking task there was observed positive within-language correlations between children's reaction times in the recognition of familiar words and vocabulary size but no significant across-language correlations. Speed of online lexical processing in Spanish showed no correlation with word stock size in English and processing speed in English was relevant for vocabulary size in Spanish. At the same time, processing speed in each language was moderately correlated with a composite vocabulary size comprising all English and Spanish words. It allowed to conclude that general processing skills that play a role in word recognition are not purely language specific.

3. Noncompliance with the mutual exclusivity constraints

In terms of other non-language specific processing skills, another profit of bilingual upbringing and advantage of enhanced word learning is bilingual children's flexibility in learning strategies, in particular, in the application of the mutual exclusivity constraint. The mutual exclusivity constraint hypothesis, suggested in 1989 by Markman basing on Slobin's earlier accounts

of syntax-based language acquisition, states that children have a bias to assume that a new label refers to an unknown object. So, when they hear a familiar sentence with an unfamiliar (made-up) word in the presence of a familiar object and of an unfamiliar object they assume that the unfamiliar word stands for the unfamiliar object. According to recent research on monolingual children, there has been found a maturational component to this bias; this tendency is not innate but develops towards the age of 2 (4).

Studies of translation equivalents in bilingual toddlers' receptive vocabulary revealed that bilinguals between 17 and 22 months old overcome the mutual exclusivity bias not only across languages but within the same language. Due to hearing multiple words for the same referent in their input, bilinguals don't assume that a new word necessarily nominates a new object, and thus, avoid following the mutual exclusivity strategy. It gives bilingual children an adaptive advantage and helps them to develop a parallel lexicon in two languages (4).

4. Enhanced metalinguistic awareness

Language competences developed in acquisition of one language can be beneficial for learning consecutive languages. Research argues the number of languages learnt and the proficiency in them can be linked to metalinguistic awareness. Nevertheless, there is no unanimous understanding of what affects what – language competences enhance the development of metalinguistic awareness or the other way round. It is likely that this is a bidirectional correlation (5).

At the same time, there are a few points of evidence *not speaking in favor* of bilingualism. Here we will discuss only one issue concerning vocabulary acquisition, though there are a few more to follow in the section on the differences between BFLA and ESLA learners.

There is clear evidence that bilingual children 3-10 y.o. persistently do worse in a word-picture association test. This remains true at least for ESLA children, for whom English was a societal language. Nevertheless, all bilinguals are different, and it makes sense to compare them to monolinguals only if the conditions for acquisition are similar (2).

A better way of assessing lexical knowledge in bilinguals is in terms of *total conceptual vocabulary*. Pearson et al. (Pearson's study of 1998 as cited in (4)) argued that, although bilingual children may have smaller lexicons compared to age-matched monolinguals, when one resorts to both languages for words to cover the semantic space the word stock proves to be similar in size regardless of language background, and possibly larger for bilinguals. Data are typically collected on children's receptive vocabulary and mostly only in English, but the studies that have addressed both receptive and expressive lexical skills have revealed that bilinguals' expressive abilities tend to lag behind those of monolinguals.

Maintaining non-native bilingualism in a monolingual context

If multilingual families reside in a place other than the parents' country/ community of origin, they have to construct and sustain their own unique identities and their childrearing and language decisions will be affected by coping with many other difficulties associated with raising children with more than one language and culture (6). Nevertheless, an opposite situation can offer similar challenges.

Non-Native Bilingualism (NNB) is not a recent trend in education and upbringing, and it dates back to as long as a few centuries ago, although recently it is regaining popularity. NNB's underlying assumption is that a parent does not speak his/her native language to the child. NNB implies neither the necessity to assimilate with the environment as early as possible (as in the case with immigration), nor the low status of L1 (subtractive bilingualism), but it is a conscious decision to speak to the child in a foreign language (a parent's L2) in a natural way (1).

In this mode of language acquisition parental involvement and input play a crucial role in the child's linguistic attainment. Nevertheless, as Romanowski (1) underscores, adjusting parental expectations is of primary importance. The input in NNB is bound to be unstable – extremely high in the early age, when the child stays in close contact with the L2 speaking parent, and inevitably decreasing as the child develops more independence. Thus, too high expectations may lead to frustration and abandonment of L2 when difficulties arise (2).

NNB families can vary in their aims. There are parents who want their children to be able to freely communicate in a language, while others may want to bring their children in contact with it, so as to prepare them for a formal instruction which they will receive at school. Achieving both goals will require a different amount of input, which will lead to different proficiency levels. Doesn't matter how smoothly acquisition goes, it is recommended to stay consistent in using L2 to communicate with the child and not resign, because even if no apparent outcomes can be observed, the passive knowledge is believed to constitute a foundation for language learning later in life.

As in NNB families the use of two languages does not result from the natural need to communicate with both parents as in international marriages, or with the society as in immigrant families, *motivation* becomes determining in the success of bilingual upbringing. Meanwhile, NNB families frequently face challenges in sustaining stable motivation. It is an often-reported issue, that the child resists L2 communication, as he or she has clear evidence that both parents are able to communicate in L1. In such cases, parents are forced to look for additional motivation, that is often difficult, as L2 needs to be linked to something intrinsically appealing, and the level of this connection has to be high and stable. As examples of such motivating outcomes of communicating in L2, there can be mentioned reading favorite books in original, watching favorite cartoons and singing songs together with parents, being able to communicate with peers in a bilingual kindergarten or

school, or with an L2-speaking babysitter, keeping in touch with monolingual relatives or travelling abroad (2). Nevertheless, to make the implementation of these recommendations successful, the parents have to establish and maintain close and trusting relationships with the child. Thus, when it comes to learning, it is the parents' responsibility to make learning L2 an attractive experience and not to impose it on the child, as this will likely discourage him or her from using it. As in NNB families, intrinsic motivation drives the whole process, both parents and children should stay motivated to ensure consistency of the process and prevent emergence of affective filters.

Apart from sustaining high motivation, another success-determining factor is the amount of L2 input. Parents should be mindful about it, and control the amount, if necessary, deliberately. According to Romanowski, 'a crucial element in catering for the child's need for a meaningful interaction in both languages are conversations' (1).

In order to internalize chunks of language the child needs a sufficient language input to analyze. It has been estimated, that about 30% (25 h a week) of all interactions should take place in L2, 20% (15 h a week) being the absolute mandatory minimum. Moreover, the most efficient acquisition takes place when the child is addressed directly, and is actively engaged in interaction. Active sources of language (talking, playing, reading) ensure higher efficiency than the passive ones (audio-books, TV), as communication with other people in itself constitutes additional motivation (1). Actually, building up sufficient input flooding, does not have to be extremely challenging, and the most straightforward way to do, apart from direct communication, it is to comment on the events and pictures while reading books as well as to interpret the emotions of the characters. It will provide appropriate *frequency of natural repetition* for the child to internalize language chunks.

In addition to providing sufficient linguistic input, it is important to apply *the child-centered mode of interaction*; it is advised to encourage their attempts to communicate through adopting such habits as active listening and letting them talk. To demonstrate interest in the conversation, adult interlocutors should ask open-ended questions, prompt lacking words and praise any production effort in the form of I-messages ("I'm glad that you speak my language"). Mistake correction and feedback should not be the main priority and break the flow of the conversation.

There is a tendency in bilingual parents to mix their languages, that can provoke unnecessary code-switching in children. If such problem arises, it is worth providing the child with a monolingual L2 interlocutor. It will require linguistic adjustment on the child's part, as prevent from resorting to code-switching to cover total conceptual vocabulary. At the same time, it will assure receiving a high-quality input, not influenced by code-switching and interference, which are common in the speech of non-native speakers (1).

Strategies of communication in the family

Adopted strategies vary across NNB families, but they should aim at the same goal of providing consistent and sufficient input. It may be necessary to adapt the chosen strategy to changing linguistic circumstances, for example increased input in societal language when the child starts a monolingual L1 kindergarten or school, and L1 becomes prevalent in their environment. Statistically, One Parent One Language (OPOL) strategy remains the most frequent in maintaining NNB.

Its advantage is that the child learns to associate a language with one of the parents, and it facilitates the choice of language to address them. It also clarifies parents' expectations of what language the child should use to respond, and helps interpret the child's first utterances. If parents are consistent in their language use, the child will develop what is called a person-language bond, that will help to make code-switching more controlled and systematic.

OPOL strategy proves to be an effective approach, because each of the languages is equally reinforced, but this may stop when the child starts kindergarten or school, and L1 exposure increases. To avoid L1 dominance, the change in approach might be required, and Minority Language at Home strategy, where both parents speak L2 at home and L1 outside the home, can be helpful. A place is considered to be the factor which triggers the language switch. This strategy provides the child with a greater exposure to L2 than in the case of OPOL. For some proponents of this approach, the place factor can be replaced with particular times when the whole family switches into L2. It can be a particular time of the day or on certain days of the week, when it is most convenient and natural to practice, or time allocated to particular routines, e.g., a visit to L2 relatives or friends, when speaking L2 is most logical. This strategy as a good option for parents who do not feel comfortable speaking L2 at all times, and whose language abilities may not allow for it.

Another option of NNB maintenance is Minority Language Immersion, when L2 is spoken by both parents at all times (at and outside home), except in the presence of those who do not speak L2. After 4–5 years, when L2 becomes considerably established, the family can switch to L1. This approach is also referred to as 'one-language-first' strategy.

Another way is Mixed Language Policy strategy, when both languages are used interchangeably, and the choice of language depends on the topic discussed, participants of the conversation, etc. It might not be 100 percent reliable as the main strategy of teaching the child L2 and maintaining it as strong as L1, as language choice is largely accidental, and there is a risk of the child not getting a sufficient input. In this case the parent should take charge to balance the amount of input in both languages.

Issues related to NNB upbringing

There are a few factors that NNB parents anticipate or face in the process of bilingual upbringing that are typically perceived as negative. In fact, it is not necessarily so, moreover, some of them contain hidden possibilities for cognitive development. These factors are:

1. Parents' L2 is not flawless

If a parent assesses their L2 proficiency as insufficient, it can prevent them from making a decision in favor of bilingual upbringing. Nevertheless, there exists research (cited in (1)) performed by an American professor of neurology Elissa Newport, who basing on her study of a deaf child learning a sign language from their deaf parents' grammatically compromised speech, concluded that the child is able to process the language far outside the input and reconstruct correct grammar rules. According to this study, a much higher level of grammatical correctness can be developed even after receiving input with occasional mistakes.

Nevertheless, it is not very clear, how low parents' proficiency can be for NNB childrearing to lead to a successful outcome. Nowadays, it is a growing trend among educators to promote the idea, that bilingualism in the child can be developed by a parent who is just a few steps ahead in L2 development compared to the child. Programs based on glossaries and situational speech scripts for parents are widely sold, advertised by claims that roleplaying these situations with a child as a part of time-bound Minority Language at Home strategy will lead to bilingualism. So, there should be limits to optimistic attitude to low L2 proficiency in parents, because the lower L2 level is, the more it has to be compensated by other factors, such as time and effort allocated to preparation for L2 speaking episodes, that will inevitably affect motivation and consistency.

2. Parents' limited vocabulary, compared to native speakers

Another issue related to the acquisition of lexis is that the child might ask for a word that a parent does not know. In fact, this obstacle opens two important doors in cognitive development; the first one is awareness that no one knows all the words of a language, even native speakers, and there are ways to expand one's thesaurus. The second door is understanding that not knowing a particular word does not have to necessarily hinder communication, and there are compensatory strategies, such as finding synonyms or giving definitions, that will allow to sustain communication if reference materials are not at hand. After the necessary vocabulary-learning or compensatory strategies are taught to the child, the main parents' responsibility is to help the child use the newly-acquired word as frequently as possible to ensure its internalization. Moreover, when conceptual gaps are identified, it is advisable that both parents provide assistance in both languages. Limiting this kind of assistance to one parent and one language might hinder the child's inborn curiosity and slow their linguistic development. Providing equivalents in both languages will, on the contrary, add to total conceptual vocabulary.

3. Unwanted code-switching/objecting to speaking L2

A common complaint among NNB families is that the child refuses to speak L2 and/or switches into L1 every time when additional effort in L2 is required. The older the children get, the better they realize that both parents speak L1, and speaking L2 starts to seem unnatural and unnecessary. Implicit encouragement, like false 'misunderstanding' of the unwanted language on the part of the parents, can bring to stronger protest. A softer way, according to Romanowski (1), could be to ignore the switch and continue the conversation in the correct language. At least, it would provide input and help the child to fill lacks and gaps that could have possibly triggered the switch.

Nevertheless, there are cases, when parents should not insist on the use of L2, for example, in the situations that are emotionally difficult for the child, or when the child gets hurt. It is only after the outbreak passes, and safety is restored, that the events can be recounted in L2.

Costa (7) in his book 'The Bilingual Brain' argues that expressing stronger emotions in dominant language is more natural than in L2, that was learnt in an academic context, as the lack of social experience in this language, restricted to the classroom, could imply a reduction in the emotional response in that language. Apart from that, emotional distancing allows better decision-making, as speaking L2 leads to considering more deliberative and logical criteria than speaking the native language. Thus, basing on abovementioned and my own experience of using OPOL method, we would hypothesize that code-switching can be strategically applied by NNB parents, for instance, for more effective anger and anxiety management, or the other way round, for establishing better emotional connections with the child in the situations of happiness or closeness.

Basing on a study of 22 Polish families, Romanowski (1) stated that 'code-switching was observed in 15 cases (68.2%), lexical transfer in 10 families (45.4%) and grammatical transfer in 6 families (27.3%). Another 6 families (27.3%) noticed other examples of code-switching behavior. i.e. shifting individual words, phrases or even sentences. The parents unanimously noticed that this occurs when their children cannot find a proper word in the language used or when a concept can be *more easily expressed in another language*. Lexical transfer was the second most common behavior, and far more ubiquitous than grammatical transfer.

Negative factors of NNB upbringing

There are a few aspects of interpersonal relationships within a family that don't look menacing at the beginning of NNB upbringing, and yet they can get damaging in the process. The degree of this impact should not be underestimated considering how long-term and consistent any L2 communication strategy needs to be to achieve any effect in language acquisition. According to Wang, the following aspects of family wellbeing are at risk:

1. Communication involvement

In OPOL families, when one parent has either zero or limited understanding of L2, the quality of family

communication suffers. Even if the family choose to relay or translate the conversation for the parent who does not understand the language being used, a lot of subtle, yet valuable information carried in the conversation will be lost. Even though the translation may be beneficial for children to learn how to express the same ideas in different languages and for parents from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds to use the opportunities to learn from each other (6), such a communication process tends to break the natural flow of conversation and can prevent participants from going deeper into the topic and continuing communication.

Moreover, such a limited communication pattern might bring up a wall between the family members, reducing time when they converse together. It will eventually lead to increasing sense of isolation, and the left-out family member will grow indifferent to what is said by the others. In the long run, there might be a risk of spillover - a negative emotional reaction transferring to other areas of family life.

2. Direct communication

In OPOL families, children may acquire a habit of 'telling on the other parent' or 'gossiping about the other parent' in their presence, believing that the other parent will not know what is being said (6). We struggle to assess, how much this trait is linked to bilingual upbringing, because we observed its bright manifestation in both bilingual and monolingual children. Probably, it would be logical to assume, that one parent's irresponsiveness to one of spoken languages could create more fertile ground for this kind of manipulative behavior, but more focused comparative research could be useful.

3. Psychological and emotional needs of children

During adolescence, thorough and dynamic child-parent conversations are necessary to understand the psychological and emotional needs of children and provide adequate support (6). This parent-child interaction can only be built in frequent communication, which is crucial for adolescent development and adaptation. Being connected by warm and close relationship, while still developing a sense of self in bilingual families can be impeded by limited proficiency of one of the interlocutors in one of the spoken languages. The other side of the coin in this situation can be possible loss of non-dominant language as a sacrifice to family liaisons.

4. Development of accountability

In NNB families, parents serve as the major conversational partners of children as well as the major L2 input providers. So, they might grow 'indulgent in ratifying children's versions of events' (6), and language used to present them, because they set and control the conversation context and are aware of their children's L2 limitations. This may result in the lack of children's accountability for making themselves understood and deepening the conversation.

5. Parental expectations

All the NNB upbringing-related issues discussed in the previous section contribute to wrong expectations on the parents' part, making them either overly anxious, or not farsighted enough. Social media only add to the distorted image of multilingual childrearing. Many parents do not have clear understanding of their

own situation and circumstance to be realistic about the challenge. Others perceive the request for consistency as something that has to be done at all cost. Needless to say, that it may result in unrealistic goals and eventually, in failure to achieve bilingualism, if not something worse. To tackle risks and possible problems, parents from monolingual environments are highly encouraged to seek support that goes beyond the language itself. To be understanding towards their children in their endeavors to acquire two languages simultaneously, parents ought to broaden their knowledge on the topic of bilingualism by reading relevant literature (1).

Differences between Bilingual First Language Acquisition (BFLA) and Early Second Language Acquisition (ESLA)

Looking at how NNB families assess their experience of bilingual parenting, Romanowski (1) found that the most popular regrets were too late beginning and insufficient input. Leaving aside that latter as undoubtedly the key factor to successful bilingual development (Gass & Mackey (8) call input 'sine qua non' of acquisition), the first argument deserves closer attention. 'The earlier, the better' is a common misconception about developing bilingualism, and as it was proven by the joint findings from studies on child bilingual development in naturalistic settings, it is not a universal principle, and is subjected to influence of many different factors (9). Naturally, different language learning environments (BFLA, ESLA, and SLA) set different trajectories of bilingual children's language acquisition by the age of 10. Outcomes can also vary, and not necessarily lead to mastery of both languages, like in cases of sequential bilingualism, when next language takes over the previous one. Another important issue to acknowledge and remember, is that not only learning trajectories, but also personal and family experience of children in BFLA and ESLA will be different.

It's worth mentioning, that in general, BFLA is three times more frequent than ESLA, because usually both the language of the society (SocL) and one other language (non-SocL) are spoken at home. In BFLA L2 input begins from birth, simultaneously with L1, that should not be confused with *simultaneous bilingualism*, when children learn different languages in the 3 first years of their life. It's different from BFLA, where children hear 2 languages from very beginning. Simultaneous bilingualism is a vague term and stands closer to ESLA, where regular L2 input begins in preschool years (2, 9). To further underscore the opaqueness of the term, it's important to remember, that De Houwer (2) distinguishes between L1 and L2 in BFLA and ESLA, referring to them as Language-A and Language-Alpha in the former and L1 and LX in the latter.

At the same time, considering the wide variety of bilingual contexts, it is worth mentioning, that L-A/L1 and L-Alpha/LX do not directly correspond to SocL and non-SocL, and their equivalence should be discussed separately for every context.

The first and most notable difference between learning trajectories in BFLA and ESLA, is that in terms of *comprehension*, in BFLA increase in

knowledge of L-A and L-Alpha happens simultaneously, from birth till age 1, and also later, till next milestone at the age 6 and further. In ESLA, comprehension of L1 forms by age 1, following the same pattern in further development too, while comprehension of LX develops much later, though also showing development until age 6 and up.

In terms of *production*, most children in BFLA start producing both L-A and L-Alpha by age 2, and increase their knowledge by 6 and up. In ESLA, though

the increase of knowledge never stops, and continues till age 6 and further, LX production starts much later (3).

Arguments for and against BFLA and ESLA strategies

Within these general tendencies discussed above, De Houwer (9) distinguishes between variations that fall into a few frequently observed patterns, representing possible language development within given age groups:

Table 1

Four patterns of language use in BFLA children age 1-6

	Understands L-A	Speaks L-A	Understands L-Alpha	Speaks L-Alpha
Pattern 1	yes	yes	yes	yes
Pattern 2	yes	yes	yes	no
Pattern 3	yes	no	yes	no
Pattern 4	no	no	no	no

Table 2

Five patterns of language use in ESLA children age 3-6

	Understands L1	Speaks L1	Understands LX	Speaks LX
Pattern 1	yes	yes	yes	yes
Pattern 2	yes	yes	yes	no
Pattern 3	yes	no	yes	no
Pattern 4	no	no	no	no
Pattern 5	yes	no	yes	yes

As it follows from the data in the tables, despite input in two languages, children may only speak a single language. The number of such cases, according to the research of 2003, can reach 25% (9). According to more recent research of 2018, up to 30% of BFLA children only speak one language, which goes against their families' expectations.

In cases when BFLA children speak only 1 language at home, according to De Houwer (2,9), it's invariably SocL, and thus the probability that they will not speak L-Alpha is much higher.

Nevertheless, ESLA children also risk losing the non-SocL, 'although this loss usually occurs at much older age than in BFLA children, who may already lose it in preschool' (9).

In contexts, similar to Minority Language Immersion strategy, when SocL is not spoken at home, and SocL becomes L-Alpha for BFLA and LX for ESLA the following acquisitional trends can be observed.

Speaking about the acquisition of the *non-societal* language, both ESLA and BFLA children show steady development in *comprehension* at ages 0-6. As for *production*, ESLA and most BFLA start producing output more or less at the same moment, in the second half of the second year of life, and the mastery of this skill develops till the age of 6 almost at the same rate as comprehension. Nevertheless, some BFLA – the representatives of those 30% mentioned earlier, show incessant decline in production starting in the second half of the third year of life.

In contrast, in the acquisition of the *societal* language up to the age of 6, no decline was observed, though in ESLA children, *comprehension* doesn't start earlier than at 3, to be followed by *production* even

later, around 4,5 years of age. The *time gap* between the beginning of comprehension and the first word-production in non-societal language is the same for ESLA and BFLA – around 8 months, but the same gap in societal language, while remaining about 8 months in BFLA, in ESLA becomes longer, and far less predictable; it can constitute from 1 month to over two years. Evidently, early child care centers, where SocL is most often learnt in ESLA, are not just language acquisition settings, but also the primary socialization units for ESLA children. Therefore, such children have to face a number of challenges, such as being suddenly put in an environment where they understand nothing and cannot express themselves even concerning basic needs. This experience may be traumatizing to a different extent, which possibly explains the longer period, when such children keep silent. Unlike them, BFLA children can avoid this break in communication due to the exposure to SocL they have received before (9).

Another important difference between BFLA and ESLA that might influence the choice between the two strategies, is the *peculiarities of morphosyntactic development in production*.

BFLA children seem to develop morphosyntax for each language separately, so that this aspect of development in one language does not influence on morphosyntax of the other language. This was given a name of Separate Development Hypothesis, and it is argued that BFLA children 'approach the morphosyntax of each language as closed sets' (2), and there is no cross-linguistic comparison. Due to this phenomenon, BFLA children's sentences are undistinguishable from those produced by their monolingual peers in each language.

In contrast, there has been some evidence that the opposite is true for ESLA; there is no separate development for each language, instead, permanent cross-linguistic influence takes place. This causes a few negative effects, such as:

1. Negative L1 transfer
2. Patterns of development are hard to predict due to
 - a. diversity of specific language pairs
 - b. the influence of children's L1 proficiency
 - c. their L2 learning opportunities

Moreover, the same correlation in mutual influence between L1 and 2 is observed in phonological development of BFLA and ESLA; BFLA tend to use appropriate phones and prosodic patterns in each of languages, while ESLA demonstrate clear influence of their L1 pronunciation on their L2.

Conclusion

In terms of advantages that bilingual childrearing can offer, such as enhanced vocabulary acquisition, higher speech processing speed, noncompliance with the mutual exclusivity constraints as an adaptive mechanism, and better metalinguistic awareness, maintaining non-native bilingualism is a worthy endeavor.

Nevertheless, it can be challenging to stay consistent in providing sufficient amount of L2 input to the child. It is crucial to ensure appropriate frequency of natural repetition for the child to internalize language units. It is also important to adopt the child-centered mode of interaction, when the child is listened to and encouraged to talk. It might be necessary to modify the amount of L2 input when the child starts L1 pre-school education, to compensate for the increasing input in L1. All these aspects of bilingual upbringing may constitute a significant burden, so, motivation becomes the main driver of NNB, and its levels should be sustained high in both the parents and the child.

Motivation can be badly affected at the very beginning, when parents are worried about their own insufficient language levels, limited vocabulary and possible protest on the child's part. In fact, these factors are not so critical for the success of developing bilingualism, and being treated mindfully, can be turned into developmental possibilities for the parents and the child.

On the other hand, such problems as hindered communication involvement of one parent, issues with direct parent-child communication, when the child keeps 'telling on the other parent', assuming that they don't understand, or when children struggle to communicate their psychological and emotional needs because of lack of fluency, can downgrade the quality of family relationships. Moreover, the child can struggle to develop accountability for their speech, as their L2-speaking parent is their main, and sometimes the only, interlocutor, who can be too indulgent, or used to guessing the meaning from familiar clues.

No matter what strategy is chosen for NNB upbringing - OPOL, Minority Language at Home, Minority Language Immersion, or Mixed Language Policy -

it is crucial to remember about differences between learning trajectories of BFLA and ESLA children, and shape expectations basing on that. Even in the first 6 years of life, all bilinguals are very different, and this is an important factor for parents and educators to inform their decision making. BFLA and ESLA children are different in terms of comprehension and production in L2. They face different struggles, for instance, BFLA children can lose non-SocL when input in SocL increases, and they might do worse in word-picture association tests. In turn, ESLA children can keep silent for as long as 2 years and suffer from severe frustration being suddenly exposed to SocL. Also, in ESLA children, there is no separate development for each language, and permanent cross-linguistic influence takes place with quite a few negative effects to follow. They frequently resort to negative L1 transfer to compensate for lacks in L2, their developmental patterns are hard to predict because of the influence of children's L1 proficiency, L2 learning opportunities, and diversity of specific language pairs.

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